

USEFULNESS OF TECHNOLOGICAL ASSISTED TEXT BOOK AS LEARNING RESOURCE IN THE TEACHING LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract:

Education must always be based on the recent situation or scenario. Education should be oriented to the present situation and not to past. Time changes and so does educational the scenario. We need to learn and understand the new techniques to study. Learning is the act of acquiring or modified and reinforcing existing, behaviours, skills, values, or preferences which may lead to potential changes in synthesizing information, depth of the knowledge, attitude or behaviour related to the type and range of experience. Learning leads to changes in the organism and the changes produced are relatively permanent. As the time changed audio-visual material came ahead. It was in the form of OHP, cassettes, songs small clips. Over the time this too has changed. Technology took strong leap in educational sector. This study uncovered the usefulness of technological assisted textbook. A sample were selected 1. on the basis of Upper Primary school and Secondary school 240 teachers, 240 students and 240 parents of NMMC school, Government aided school & Private school and also from Upper Primary and Secondary Section. This research will be survey method for studying usefulness of Technological Assisted text book in the teaching learning process. With the help of questionnaires researcher will check the opinion of teachers, students and parents of students of Municipal School, Government aided and private school. To study the nature of the data

and differences between various variables of the study, the researcher made use of inferential statistics technique. For the purpose of inferential analysis of the data in the present study, T-test and ANOVA was used to find out the relationship between various dimensions. The values of standard deviation used to measure the trade or actions of scores in sample each hypothesis is tested with T test and ANOVA. Usefulness for Teachers, students and parents of Municipal school teacher is good but the analysis shows that Government aided and Private school teachers found it difficult in accessing the QR code. It could be because of lack of knowledge regarding QR code. The analysis shows that government aided school students face a few more difficulties compared to the other school students.

Challenges faced by teachers, students and parents could be some teachers are not aware of QR Code or DIKSHA APP, or they need training for using it. Issues faced by them, could be Internet service, lack of technological knowledge or they might be not aware of QR Code.

Keywords: *Usefulness, Technology, Textbook, Teaching Learning Resources, Teachers, Students, Parents.*

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Introduction:

“The purpose of utilizing teaching and learning resources in school is to help and understand the teacher with the presentation and transmission of educational content. Therefore the achievement of educational objectives, whilst aiding the students in acquiring knowledge and profiling different abilities and values. Here is the list of the common goals: 1. Student motivation, 2. Developing creativity, 3. Evoking prior knowledge, 4. encouraging the process of understanding, decoding, organizing and synthesizing the educational content, logical thinking and reasoning, communication and interaction. Even outside the context of teaching, teaching and learning resources have their own value and a special impact on individuals. For example, viewing a photograph or painting can give rise to different memories and emotions or encourage creativity in an individual. If the aforementioned is applied to the teaching and learning process, we will deduce that the goal of using teaching and learning resources should be directing the reaction, primarily caused by these resources, towards the ability and achievement of the set goals and objectives of teaching. Method of education. Montessori methods of

teaching based on observation, this method is based on idea that children learn best when the environment supports. Edger Del: Edger Del was an American educator who developed the cone of experience. He made several contributions to audio & visual instructions.

Technology in textbook: Formal education is given by specially qualified teachers. Teachers use various methods like lecture, discussion, demonstration, role plays, team teaching while teaching in class room. Teachers need to enhance their teaching skills by using innovative teaching strategies with the help of effective learning resources. The use of this material was started in the form of small cards, pictures, letters and tables .In recent advances new changes had taken place in education material .The audio materials were now replaced by audio-visual tools. Educational materials were available in the form of Cassette and Cd. Moreover there are online classes provided to make education or studying easy in the forms of apps and online tutors. Technology has taken a strong leap in different sectors. We can see step vies the growth of technology. Education sectors are not far from this progress. Studies have changed a lot in terms of teaching methods. We look forward to the positive changes in education as per the need of hour. Early learning methods were teacher centric and later it becomes a student centric.

The state government of Maharashtra had put forward the introduction of e content with QR code in diksha app (Digital infrastructure for knowledge sharing) and was executed in the year 2019. With a technical support and backup of EkStep. With the main objective of making textbook material available for students and teachers on a digital platform using QR code.It covered all mediums (English, Hindi, Marathi, Urdu, Telegu, Malayalam etc.) all standards (1-10) and all subjects. Approximately 13,600 QR code are to be put in place with virtue of 586 teachers was initiated from Maharashtra.

Review of Related Literature:

Nair Sobhana Nandakumar (2017) conducted a study on “**Impact of New Trends of Teaching Learning Process in Mathematics towards the Competitiveness of Female students at Higher Secondary Schools in Mumbai**”. Education May be a dynamic method it changes with time in step with the necessity of society. If the system of education steps to change itself to dynamical state of affairs the progress can halt. The researcher wanted to explore the impact of new trends of teaching learning process in Mathematics towards the competitiveness of female students at higher Secondary in Mumbai School. The researcher wanted to study the impact /influence of new trends of

learning also encourage usage of new trends in education to facilitate equal representation of females in professional courses. The study found the impact of new trends by comparing the scores of std XI class of two groups (Experimental and Control group) by teaching the topic Angles and measures from Trigonometry (prescribed syllabus of Maharashtra state board of Higher secondary).

Objectives Of the study

1. To study the impact of new Trends of teaching learning process in mathematics towards female students.
2. To study the new trends in maths teaching learning.
3. To study the relation between competitive risk of female students and new Trends of teaching learning process.
4. To find out the female student's attitude towards professional courses with the impact of nutrients of teaching learning process.
5. To study the attitude of female students of aided and unaided school towards the new trends in teaching learning mathematics.

Shaik Anwar Basha F (2017), conducted study on ‘**Effectiveness of programmed learning method in learning social science among school students at Kallakurichi educational district.**’

There are individual differences among children in terms of level of intelligence, level of understanding, attitudes, achievements et cetera therefore the same type of institutional method in classroom may not be issued to the classroom situations to cater to the need needs of individual differences and abilities we have to adopt innovative instructional procedure the national policy on education has emphasised the need of qualitative improvement of school education. The new education policy 1986 envisages a Drift from traditional lecture method to an approach that has a focus on learner. Program instruction in a subhead under instruction and represent a more rigorous attempt to develop a mastery over specified goals to secure insure learning. The present study has an attempt to test the effectiveness of social science in secondary. school level it is hoped that the study would contribute some highlights to words new approach of teaching.

Objectives of learning social science:

1. To appreciate the values enshrined in the Indian enshrined such as Justice liberty equality and the unity and integrity of the nation and building of a socialist, secular and democratic society.
2. To grow as active, responsible and reflective members of society.

3. To question and examine received ideas, instructions and practises.
4. To undertake activities that will help them to develop social and life skills.

Objectives of the study:

1. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the pre-test score in social science between control and experimental group statements of standard eight.
 2. Find out whether there is a significant difference in the pre-test scores in social science between control and experimental group students of standard eight with respect to gender, locality, type of schools, parent's education and occupation.
 3. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the post test score in social science between control and experimental group students of standard eight with respect to gender locality type of school's parent education and occupation.
 4. To find out whether there is any significant difference between protest and post test score in social science among the experimental group students of standard eight. To find out whether there is any significant difference between the post-test and retention test score in social science among experimental group students of standard eight.
- Findings of the study-The results of the study reveal that learning through program learning method helps to improving the achievement of students, in general and enhance ability of learners in the skills such as knowledge understanding application of social science concepts in particular hence, it is the need of the day to develop and introduce such model for better teaching learning process at school level.

Richa Sharma, A research journal December 2020 study on “**Comparative study MOOC learning and blended learning in teaching learning process.**” The purpose of the study is to find out the differences between learning and blended learning in the teaching learning process. The sample was taken from the school.

Objectives of the study:

1. The main objective of the study is to find out the comparison between MOOC learning and blended learning the present research is normative survey research.

Findings of the study:

1. Blended learning in which a combination of online learning and a traditional classroom can be followed by THE approach to sustain the quality and efficacy of the learning. This method shall not only accelerate academic achievement but it will also develop a practical skill said as well.
2. Blended strategy is better than MOOC.

Garba bala Doguwa, July 2021, “Analysis of availability and uses of information and Communication Technology (ICT) Resources in the Teaching of Physics in Science Secondary School in Kano State”.

Objective of the study:

1. The study analysed the information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities availability and uses in science Secondary School in Canada state.
2. To find out ICT resources availability to Physics teacher in Science Secondary School in Canada state.
3. To find out whether ICT resources are used in the teaching of Physics, by Physics teacher in Science Secondary School Kano State.

Findings of the Study:

1. The result it shows that ICT resources are not available in most of the Science School and that most Physics teacher do not utilize even the few available ICT resources in teaching physics.

Suggestion of the Study:

1. Government and Non-governmental organization should work hard to speak in effective teaching learning of Physics.
2. The study has revealed that ICT resources are not available in reasonable number in majority of the science Secondary School in chemistry.
3. The available ICT resources are not utilized properly by Physics teacher despite the impact of ICT resources in physics education.

Mr. Pushendra Yadav, (July 2021), “Challenges faced by School Education system in online assessment in the face of sudden switch to ICT based Teaching-Learning”.

In the past few months, we all have affected by covid-19 pandemic. From March 2020 schools and colleges where closed due to increased cases of covid-19 across India. We can say this was one of the biggest pandemics of the country. We all remain closed in our home with proper distancing in this pandemic lot of things in our habit, lifestyle and behaviour has been changed. In this pandemic our education system completely relies on online /ICT based teaching and learning because besides there is no alternative left for us.

Purpose of assessment:

1. To know about the suitability of learning style needed by the learner and teacher

at the same time.

2. To understand the difficulties faced by the learner in opting.
3. Do you know what kind of training can be help the teacher better in the process of teaching and learning.
4. The aim of assignment also lies in framing how the necessary modifications required in the curriculum for whole sum or Holistic education.

Conclusions:

1. Online teaching and ICT based teaching and learning was only medium during the period of pandemic.
2. The experience of the past few months teaches us norms for assessment should be change on various expect especially if we implement it through online mode.
3. Policy maker must develop and design documents module related to online assessment.

Suggestions:

1. Training of student teacher and staff of school provided by School management for online test and also assignments.
2. Urgent need for a document or policy related to online assessment to it can work as a guide guideline and bill trust among teachers and students. For the purpose of the study, researcher has reviewed related literature from Indian studies and foreign studies. The reviews reveals that impact of technological teaching learning process is showing positive results. It was also observed that none of the study were done on finding the accessibility, usefulness and challenges of QR coded textbook usage in teaching learning process as it was newly introduced concept. So, researcher selected this topic as a part of her study.

Aims of the Study:

To study the usefulness of technological of assisted (QR Coded) textbook as a learning resource.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To compare the usefulness of technological assisted (QR coded) text books for teachers, students & Parents on the basis of type of school namely
 - a) Municipal School
 - b) Government Aided
 - c) Private Schools of Navi Mumbai

2.To compare the usefulness of technological assisted (QR coded) text books for teachers, students & Parents on the basis of level of education namely.

- a) Upper Primary school
- b) Secondary school.

Hypothesis of The Study

1. There is no significant difference in the usefulness of technological assisted (QR coded) text books for teachers, students & parents on the basis of type of school namely

- a) Municipal School
- b) Government Aided
- c) Private Schools of Navi Mumbai

2. There is no significant difference in the usefulness of technological assisted (QR coded) text books for teachers, students & parents on the basis of level of education namely

- a) Upper Primary
- b) Secondary school.

Delimitations of the Study:

1. A representative sample of Upper Primary and Secondary school Teachers, Students and Parents are selected from ten educational clusters of Navi Mumbai. The selected teachers, students and parents are from state board of English, Hindi and Marathi medium.

2. A representative sample of Municipal schools, Government aided Schools and Private schools Teachers, Students and Parents are selected from ten educational clusters of Navi Mumbai. The selected teachers, students and parents are from state board of English, Hindi and Marathi medium.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

Survey method: This research will be survey method for studying usefulness of Technological Assisted text book in the teaching learning process. With the help of questionnaires researcher will check the opinion of teachers, students and parents of students of Municipal School, Government aided and private school. Following collection of data, will be analysed and relation between the dependent variables will be analysed.

Sample:

A research population is generally a large collection of individual or objects that is the main focus of a scientific query. A research population is also known as a well-defined collection of individuals or objects known to have similar characteristics. The entire population here refers to teachers, students and parents of upper primary and secondary schools from municipal schools, government aided school and Private school from Navi Mumbai, Thane districts. Only upper primary and secondary school teachers and students and parents will be selected through random sampling.

- i) Teachers of upper primary and secondary section of Municipal School, Government aided and private school.
- ii) Students of upper primary and secondary section of Municipal School, Government aided and private school.
- iii) Parents of students of upper primary and secondary section of Municipal School, Government aided and private school.

Tools Used:

A research tool plays a major role in any worthwhile research as it is the factor for determining the perfect conclusion of the study. It is necessary to adopt a systematic procedure to collect essential data. Relevant data, adequate in quantity and quality should be collected. The instruments thus employed as means for collecting data are called tools. The selection of suitable instruments or tools is of vital importance for successful research.

For the purpose of present study, the researcher will use three tools to collect information from teachers, students and parents of students of Municipal School, Government aided and private school. These include researcher made tools.

A. Researcher made tools: Questionnaires for teachers, students, and parents' opinion, about technological assisted text book in teaching process.

Validity of Tool:

For the purpose of checking validity of the tool, Content validity was done by five experts.

Reliability of Tool:

The researcher established the reliability of the tool through Kuder and Richardson formula of reliability. The result of the reliability of the tool is as follows.

Reliability of Tool: Kuder and Richardson formula = 0.81

Procedure:

For the purpose of the study the researcher followed the following procedure.

1. Researcher took the permission from the Principal of Municipal School, Government aided School and Private School. These schools were selected from ten Educational clusters of Navi Mumbai.
2. Researcher made questionnaire in English language. Some students were from Marathi medium, so may be students and parents will get it difficult to understand the questionnaire. So as per need the researcher has translated the questionnaire in Marathi.
3. Teachers-240, Students-240, Parents-240 were selected from Municipal School, Government aided School and Private School for the study. Google form link was forwarded to the teachers. Teachers forwarded it to students and parents. Thus the data collection was done.
4. For the present study two types of analysis were done that is descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. A descriptive statistical measure studies the characteristics of particular group. The generalization is limited up to the particular group studied. The conclusion cannot be extended beyond the group. For the present study the statistical measures used for descriptive analysis were of measure of Central tendency (mean, median and mode) and Measure of variability (standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis) are included.

Results:

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of USEFULNESS of technological assisted (QR Coded) textbooks for the total Sample.

The following table gives the measures of central tendency and variability of Usefulness for Teachers, Students and Parents of total sample.

Variable	Sample Size	Mean	Median	Mode	Standard Deviation	Kurtosis	Skewness
Usefulness	720	35.74	37.00	39.00	3.83	0.30	-1.00

Interpretation of descriptive analysis of Usefulness of technological assisted (QR Coded) textbooks for the total Sample.

The mean, median and mode of Usefulness for the total sample of Teachers, Students and Parents are in the ascending order. The Skewness is -1.00 which is negative. So, the data

is negatively skewed. The kurtosis is 0.30 it is less than standard value 3. Hence the distribution is said to be platykurtic.

PERCENTAGE OF TEACHERS, STUDENTS & PARENTS FOR USEFULNESS OF TECHNOLOGICAL ASSISTED TEXT BOOK.

USEFULNESS							
NO	STATEMENT	Teachers		Students		Parents	
		YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO
1.	The QR coded e-content is helpful in the teaching learning process.	92%	8%	88%	12%	89%	11%
2.	The QR Coded e-content is a better option than any other teaching learning resource.	75%	25%	82%	18%	79%	21%
3.	It is not beneficial for self-study	25%	75%	30%	70%	27%	73%
4.	It is effective for self-learning of all the subjects.	83%	17%	81%	19%	82%	18%
5.	DIKSKA APP is not a useful App in teaching learning process..	22%	78%	26%	74%	29%	71%
6.	It makes the teaching learning process more interesting.	85%	15%	88%	12%	82%	18%
7.	It helps to understand the difficult concepts better.	100%	0%	88%	12%	86%	14%
8.	It helps the user to get deeper insight to the concept.	88%	12%	87%	13%	87%	13%
9.	It does not provide instant feedback..	38%	62%	33%	67%	34%	66%
10.	It gives enriched material.	80%	20%	84%	16%	82%	18%
11.	It does not give concept clarity..	31%	69%	33%	67%	37%	63%
12.	It provides ample scope for enriching to the concept.	86%	14%	86%	14%	83%	17%
13.	It makes the learning of difficult concept easier.	88%	12%	88%	12%	87%	13%
14.	It creates interest among the learners.	90%	10%	85%	15%	88%	12%

15.	Learners cannot learn at their own pace.	30%	70%	36%	64%	68%	32%
16.	It is helpful for the slow learner.	81%	19%	86%	14%	88%	12%
17.	It is a guide to know more about the concept of the text book.	90%	10%	91%	9%	88%	12%
18.	It does not have practical work.	45%	55%	43%	57%	46%	54%
19.	It is prepared as per the level of the students.	88%	12%	85%	15%	84%	16%
20.	It does not include variety of e-content.	36%	64%	40%	60%	49%	51%

Conclusion: Approximately 68% of teachers says that DIKSHA APP is useful in teaching learning process. It helps to understand difficult concepts. QR Coded e-content creates interest among students. It gives enrich material. It is prepared as per the level of the students. While 32% teachers says that it does not gives concept clearly. Teachers says that students or learners cannot learn at their own pace. They will require a basic training to understand the same.

Conclusion: Approximately 68% of students says that DIKSHA APP and QR coded e-content is useful for self-learning. It is a guide to know more about the concept of the text book. It helps to understand difficult concepts. QR Coded e-content creates interest among students. It gives enrich material. It is prepared as per the level of the students. While 32% teachers says that it does not gives concept clearly. Teachers says that students or learners cannot learn at their own pace. It does not include verity of e-content. Students require a basic training to understand the same.

Conclusion: Approximately 70% of parents says that DIKSHA APP and QR coded e-content is useful for self-learning. It is a guide to know more about the concept of the text book. It helps to understand difficult concepts. QR Coded e-content creates interest among students. It gives enrich material. It is prepared as per the level of the students. While 30% teachers says that it does not gives concept clearly. Teachers says that students or learners cannot learn at their own pace. It does not include verity of e-content. Parents require a basic training to understand the same.

Interpretation:

Approximately 88% teachers students and parents found that QR code air content is helpful in teaching learning process. Round about 79% of teachers students and parents the QR code it we can give better option than any other resource. Approximately only 27 % of teachers students and parents are saying that there could be contained is beneficial for self-study. Approximately 82% of teacher's students and parents are saying that it is effective for self-learning of all the subjects. 85% of teacher students and parents found that QR coded e content makes the teaching learning process more interesting. 100% of teachers, 80% of students says that QR Coded e-content helps to understand difficult concept better. 35 % of teachers, students and parents face that with does not give concept clarity. Approximate 44% student's teachers and parents save that learners cannot learn at their own true where are around about 85% teachers, students and parents found that it is useful for slow learner. Approximately 45% teacher students and parents says that it does not provide opportunity to practical work. 86% of teachers, students and parents says that the QR Coded e-contains is prepared as per level of students, on the other hand, approximately 42% teachers, students and parents says that it does not include variety of e-content.

Overall Discussion:

Usefulness

Usefulness for teachers of Municipal school, government aided school and private school, analysis show that private school teachers are facing problems while using QR codes. On the other hand, Municipal school teachers find less difficulties in accessing the QR code. Analysis of Usefulness for students of Municipal school, government aided school and private school, shows that Municipal school students are facing less problems while using QR codes. Issues faced students of government aided school and private school, could be Internet service, lack of knowledge about QR code or understanding the E-content etc. Usefulness for Parents of government aided school and private school faces a few difficulties compared to Municipal school parents. Issues faced parents, could be Internet service or they might be not aware of QR Code.

Suggestions

Suggestions to improve Usefulness for Teachers, Students and Parents.

It is necessary to conduct training sessions of awareness of QR coded textbook for teachers. They should get proper guidance of using it. They should know how the internet issues could be solved. It is necessary to conduct training sessions of awareness of QR

coded textbook for Students. Students should know how to scan it , how it is useful for self-study.

Parents are the main factor who are going make the access of smartphones for students. It is necessary to conduct a session for the awareness of QR coded textbooks. In this pandemic parents try to help out the students by providing their cells. But for some parents net package was also hurdle in accessing this facility. So with the help of training session, parents doubts could be resolve.

References:

1. Denso Wave (Archived from the original on 12 May 2013) “QR Code features”.
2. DIKSHA NCTE APP User Manual (SCERT / Balbharti / LFE Pune)
3. Kothari C.R: Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques; Wiley Eastern Limited, Second Edition, 4th Reprint 1993.
4. Ranjit Kumar. (1996) Research Methodology: A step-by-step Guide for Beginners.
5. Panneerselvam R. Research Methodology.
6. Samant D.G. (1996) the Making of Educational Research; Popular Prakash an, Bombay.

Theses:

7. Nair Sobhana Nandakumar (2017) conducted a study on “Impact of New Trends of Teaching Learning Process in Mathematics towards the Competitiveness of Female students at Higher Secondary Schools in Mumbai”.
8. Shaik Anwar Basha F (2017), conducted study on ‘Effectiveness of programmed learning method in learning social science among school students at Kallakurichi educational district.’
9. Richa Sharma, A research journal December 2020 study on “Comparative study MOOC learning and blended learning in teaching learning process.”
10. Mr. Pushpendra Yadav, (July 2021), “Challenges faced by School Education system in online assessment in the face of sudden switch to ICT based Teaching-Learning”.
11. Garba bala Doguwa, July 2021, “Analysis of availability and uses of information and Communication Technology (ICT) Resources in the Teaching of Physics in Science Secondary School in Kano State”.

Sites:

12. <https://www.statisticsshowto.com>

13. <https://qualtrics.com/au/experience-management/research/anova>
14. <https://www.thoughtco.com>
15. <https://www.simplypsychology.org.com>
16. <https://www.real-statistics.com>
17. <https://www.iedunote.com>
18. <https://method.sagepub.com>
19. <https://www.linkspringer.com>
20. <https://guides.library.bloomu.com>
21. <https://www.investopedia.com>
22. <https://www.editage.com>
23. <https://www.questionpro.com>
24. <https://libguides.usc.edu.com>
25. <https.leverageedu.com>
26. <https://www.slideshare.net>
27. <https://researchgate.net>
28. <https://research-methodology.net>